

Literacy Intervention Strategies for Increasing Kindergarteners' Letter Sound Fluency and Word Recognition: A Proposed Intervention

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Abstract

This research sought to determine the effectiveness of the following proposed literacy intervention strategies: perfect match, fluency letter wheel, letter flash, familiar word readings, word relay, and fast match in increasing letter sound fluency and word recognition among kinder pupils enrolled in Manggolod Elementary School of Sta. Catalina District III. Forty-two (42) respondents were equally distributed among three groups based on their level of intelligence per academic grades from first to second quarter. The study utilized the standardized Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) as the tool in determining the pre-test and post-test performance of the kinder pupils. The researcher prepared 3 different intervention strategies for letter sound fluency and 3 different intervention strategies for word recognition and administered them to the pupils. To check on the effectiveness of the strategies, a post-test was conducted using EGRA. Results were statistically treated using percentage, weighted mean, t-test for independent data and t-test for dependent data. It was found out that pre-test and post-test performance of the kinder pupils in letter sound fluency and word recognition was generally within satisfactory level. Post-test performance in letter sound fluency and word recognition was also remarkable. There was a significant difference between their pre-test and post-test performance in letter sound fluency word recognition intervention activities. Hence, it is recommended that other schools would use the strategies proposed in this study so to compare the findings of this study.

Keywords: Literacy intervention strategies, Letter sound fluency, Word recognition

Introduction

The Department of Education (DepEd) believes that Kindergarten is the transition period from informal to formal literacy, considering that age five (5) is within the critical years in which positive experiences must be nurtured to ascertain school readiness (K to 12 Kindergarten Curriculum Guide, 2016).

It is a known fact that pupils enter kindergarten with differing abilities. While other pupils coming in to kindergarten are not well-versed with alphabet knowledge, other kinder pupils can already read and write recognizable words. Letter sound and letter naming are no longer the things a kindergarten should learn in this stage; they also have to meet the standards set forth and have to master letters and letters sound by the end of the school year (Schultz, 2015).

A preschooler, who is already well-versed with letter naming and sounding, will have no difficulty in acquiring the basics of reading and spelling. However, when pupils, especially kindergarten, fall short from the standards set by the curricula that they must be properly acquainted with letter sounds and names, they will likely find it hard to catch up with others and will have difficulty in learning to read (cited in Schultz, 2015).

Research has indicated that a large percentage of primary-grade students who struggle in reading have not achieved full competency in the foundational reading competencies (word recognition and fluency in letter naming and sounding). More on intensive instruction of the foundational competencies should be done and a simple lesson approach should be prepared to help improve the reading outcomes of students who struggle (Rasinski, 2017).

However, it is evident that year after year, as per researcher observation, the level of proficiency in terms of reading is declining, and the number of non-readers by the end of grade 3 is growing in an alarming rate. It is quite a dilemma since most of the teachers fail to take into account that letter sound fluency and word recognition of kinder pupils are early determiners of their future literacy skills.

Several studies have already been conducted as to the perceived importance and effect if fluency (both in letter sound and word recognition) have been developed in an early age, and lots of literacy practices are now made readily available for the consumption of teachers to better enhance letter sound fluency and word recognition. Unfortunately, in the light of all these practices, the mastery level of kinder pupils in terms of letter sounds and word could not meet the benchmarks. It was on this premise that the researcher decided to tackle this issue, considering that the researcher is also a school reading coordinator.

The researcher believed that letter sound fluency and word recognition should be given great emphasis in kinder pupils because this will help them attain early literacy at an early age. The researcher proposed an innovated intervention on how to effectively teach letter sound fluency and word recognition.

The relationship between a pupil's letter sound and word recognition knowledge, especially at the beginning of kindergarten, plays a significant role in that pupil's future success in reading and writing. The researcher also hoped to provide information for teachers regarding literacy strategies to implement with pupils who are struggling with learning letter sounds and word recognition to increase pupils' alphabet knowledge skills. The researcher also sought to spread awareness to teachers who are not aware of the significance of the correlation between a pupil's letter acquisition skills and their future literacy success.

Furthermore, the insight gained from the study would inform the thinking of present and future educators regarding the best practices and approaches to use to aid in early childhood students' acquisition of early literacy skills.

Research Design

The study is descriptive and experimental in nature. It is descriptive since it identified the effectiveness of the proposed intervention activities in increasing letter sound fluency and word recognition of kinder pupils. It is also experimental in nature since it tested the intervention strategies to see if these strategies would make a difference. There were three (3) sets of respondents for letter sound fluency intervention strategies. The same number and set of respondents were also utilized for word recognition intervention strategies. Kinder pupils were assigned and grouped equally. There was a pre-test and a post-test for the three sets of respondents.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in Manggolod Elementary School, a public elementary school of Sta. Catalina District III. The school is situated far from the national highway.

The aforementioned school has seven (7) regular teachers and one (1) school principal. The school has the necessary facilities such as electrical connection, water supply, and computer laboratories essential to foster quality learning. Common source of income for the residents is planting sugar cane.

Research Respondents

There were three (3) sets of respondents to this study, three groups for letter sound fluency and the same groups were utilized for word recognition activities. These three groups were formed equally from the forty-two kinder pupils of the abovementioned school. The three sets of respondents had members whose level of knowledge is equally distributed among them. The level of intelligence was identified through their classroom performance and academic performance of each pupil for the first and second quarter. This was done to avoid bias or advantage to a certain group and so that the researcher would truly find out what strategy yielded the best result.

Research Instruments

The study utilized the standardized Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) translated in Sinugbuanong Binisaya issued by the Department of Education under DepEd Order No. 57 Utilization of the Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) and Early Grade Math Assessment (EGMA) Tools for System Assessment (2015), which is adopted from the RTI International (2009). This standardized letter sound fluency and word recognition test instrument was used during the pre-test in determining the extent of letter sound fluency and word recognition of kinder pupils. And in the post test, EGRA was still utilized to determine the difference of test results from the pre test against the post test after the proposed intervention strategies had been presented. Through this, the researcher knew what strategies yielded positive result. The researcher also utilized the Revised DIBELS 6th Edition Benchmark Goals (2014) to interpret the result of the EGRA in determining the letter sound and word use or recognition fluency (EGRA Toolkit-RTI International, 2009).

Research Procedure

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher sought the permission of the Division Superintendent. Upon the approval, the researcher scheduled the administration of the tests and put into test the proposed literacy intervention strategies in order to avoid inconvenience and unpreparedness on the part of the respondents.

The EGRA questionnaires were personally conducted and delivered to the respondents with the attached cover letter stating the instruction and purpose of the study.

After administering the pre-test, grouping was made and the class was divided into three (3). The three sets of respondents were subjected to three different intervention strategies for letter sound fluency namely perfect match for group 1, fluency letter wheel for group 2, and letter flash for group 3. After that, the same sets of respondents were subjected to three different intervention strategies this time for word recognition namely familiar word readings for group 1, word relay for group 2, and fast match for group 3. Detailed lesson plans for each activity both in letter sound fluency and word recognition was used so that the researcher would be properly guided as to the administration of the proposed interventions.

A post-test was conducted for letter sound fluency and word recognition after all the intervention strategies had been done. This would measure and would determine the effectiveness of the proposed interventions and which of them yield the best result.

Confidentiality of the results and other data collected was assured to the respondents and that no names would be mentioned relative to this.

Findings

Table 1. Pre-test Performance of the Kinder Pupils in Letter Sound Fluency

Group	Rating	Verbal Description
Group 1 (n=14)	83.07	Satisfactory
Group 2 (n=14)	85.93	Very Satisfactory
Group 3 (n=14)	87.07	Very Satisfactory

Legend:

Rating Scale	Descriptor
90%-100%	Outstanding
85% - 89%	Very Satisfactory
80% - 84%	Satisfactory
75% - 79%	Fairly Satisfactory
Below 74%	Did Not Meet Expectations

As shown in Table 1, all three groups got a rating of not less than 80%. Group 1 performed satisfactorily with a rating of 83.07%; group 2 with a rating of 85.93% and 3 with a rating of 87.07% were very satisfactory. This result indicates that the performance of the kinder pupils were able to meet the expectations set based on DepEd Order No. 8 (2015).

The proposed literacy intervention strategies, in this case, would act as enrichment to them, making them more fluent than they are now.

However, this result also indicates that there are some learners who perform beneath the set mark based on their raw scores before the grades were transmuted. Being in the fourth quarter of the school year already, kinder pupils must already be well-versed in letter sound fluency as this is one of the most basic skills they must learn before entering grade 1.

Being fluent in letter sound is one of the imperative requirements kinder pupils must attain so to become successful readers in the future. This percentage of pupils who barely passed or met the set mark must not be neglected and should receive proper and immediate action to save them from failing and worst becoming non-readers. This is in line with the findings of Learning First Alliance (2000) which suggested that children who have poorly developed letter sound fluency at the end of kindergarten are likely to become poor readers.

To sum up, kinder pupils whose performance was “very satisfactory” could still benefit from the proposed intervention strategies by using them as enrichment activities. To pupils whose performance was “satisfactory,” the proposed strategies would be of great help to them.

This is still in consonance with the study of Schultz (2015) which revealed that letter sound and letter naming are no longer the things a kindergarten should learn in this stage; they also have to meet the standards set forth and have to master letters and letters sound by the end of the school year.

Table 2. Pre-test Performance of the Kinder Pupils in Word Recognition

Group	Rating	Verbal Description
Group 1 (n=14)	78.71	Fairly Satisfactory
Group 2 (n=14)	79.93	Satisfactory
Group 3 (n=14)	80.57	Satisfactory

Legend:

Rating Scale	Descriptor
90%-100%	Outstanding
85% - 89%	Very Satisfactory
80% - 84%	Satisfactory
75% - 79%	Fairly Satisfactory
Below 74%	Did Not Meet Expectations

In Table 2, it is evident that the kinder pupils' performance also met the standards set. Groups 2 and 3 attained satisfactory passing scores with a rating of 79.93 and 80.57%, respectively. Although these two groups attained satisfactory rating, it is still alarming to note that Group 1 got 78.71% under "fairly satisfactory." This result indicates that kinder pupils who are not properly acquainted with letter sound knowledge will have difficulty recognizing even basic and familiar words.

This is in line with the results of Learning First Alliance (2000) which states that knowledge of sound-symbol associations is vital for success in kindergarten and beyond. Accurate and fluent word recognition depends on phonics knowledge. The ability to read words accounts for a substantial proportion of overall reading success even in older readers. When good readers encounter an unknown word, they decode the word, name it, and then attach meaning.

To sum up, the result of the kinder pupils administered with the pre-test shows that there are still pupils who perform poorly as compared to other. And their number is not something that is negligible. Performing "fairly satisfactory" cannot warrant success in future literacy skills and must be intervened as soon as possible. This is in line with the study of Wolf (2016) showing that early intervention on letter sound reading increased significantly the word recognition abilities of kinder children.

Table 3. Posttest Performance of the Kinder Pupils in Letter Sound Fluency

Group	Rating	Verbal Description
Group 1 (Perfect Match)	85.00	Very Satisfactory
Group 2 (Fluency Letter Wheel)	94.64	Outstanding
Group 3 (Letter Flash)	87.86	Very Satisfactory

Legend:	Rating Scale	Descriptor
	90%-100%	Outstanding
	85% - 89%	Very Satisfactory
	80% - 84%	Satisfactory
	75% - 79%	Fairly Satisfactory
	Below 74%	Did Not Meet Expectations

In Table 3, it is clearly depicted that among the three sets of respondents, Group 2 got the rating of 94.64%, highest among the three with "outstanding" performance. Groups 1 and 3, attaining a rating of 85.00 and 87.86%, respectively, also had improvement in their scores but not that high. The results presented in this table suggest that through literacy intervention strategies, pupils who perform well in class were enriched even more, thereby attaining scores that met the set mark. On the other hand, pupils who did not meet expectation and those who barely passed showed positive and significant improvement in their performance that made them attain higher scores. The literacy intervention strategies, therefore, helped the kinder pupils attain this improvement.

This result is on consonance with Brooks' (2007) result which suggested that when it comes to failing readers at the end of kindergarten, ordinary class teaching is not enough and specialized literacy interventions are required. Structured specialized intervention for failing readers is more effective than eclectic approaches. This is not to suggest that there should not be a balanced approach to the various elements of a literacy curriculum but to emphasize the importance of targeted teaching that is structured, explicit and systematic.

According to the report of the National Reading Panel (2000), it is also repeatedly stressed that there is concrete evidence as to the effectiveness of systematic approaches, particularly in the teaching of phonology or sound symbol knowledge.

As shown in Table 4, there is a "very high" extent of implementation of instructional supervision as perceived by both of the novice and experienced teachers in the aspect of concept and

purpose of instructional supervision. This implies that both categories of teachers demonstrate greater understanding and display higher awareness on the significance of the conduct of instructional supervision as a tool for teacher’s growth.

Instructional supervision is very important to the development of education and it is fitting to establish how it is perceived by teachers in schools. Unless teachers perceive supervision as a process of improving learning conditions and promoting professional growth, the supervisory exercise will not achieve its desired purpose. Researchers also attached numerous purposes to instructional supervision: improving classroom instruction, providing specific direction, fostering curriculum innovations, improving performance evaluation, encouraging human relations and supporting collaboration (Payne, 2010; Awuah, 2011; Wanzare, 2012).

The result shown in the table is in conjunction to the study of Kuizon and Reyes (2014) that collaborative approach to supervision is mostly favoured by instructional supervisors. Moreover, the findings in the study of Hoffman and Tesfaw (2012) show that both beginner and experienced teachers were convinced of the need for instructional supervision, and believe that every teacher can benefit from instructional supervision. Teachers also welcome supervision if it is done in the right spirit and with the aim of improving the learning process and promoting teacher growth. Finally, Tshabalala (2013) found out that teachers generally perceive classroom instructional supervision in a positive way. They are aware of what it is and appreciated its purpose.

Table 4. Posttest Performance of the Kinder Pupils in Word Recognition

Group	Rating	Verbal Description
Group 1 (Familiar Word Readings)	78.86	Fairly Satisfactory
Group 2 (Word Relay)	81.93	Satisfactory
Group 3 (Fast Match)	92.86	Outstanding

Legend:	Rating Scale	Descriptor
	90%-100%	Outstanding
	85% - 89%	Very Satisfactory
	80% - 84%	Satisfactory
	75% - 79%	Fairly Satisfactory
	Below 74%	Did Not Meet Expectations

In Table 4, it is depicted that Groups 1 and 2 increased slightly in their performance. Group 1 got a “fairly satisfactory” rating of 78.86%, while Group 2 landed an 81.93% “satisfactory” rating. Among the three groups, the performance of Group 3 is the most notable for having an “outstanding” rating of 92.86%, highest among the three. This indicates that after the literacy intervention strategies had been conducted, improvement in terms of word recognition is evident among the three groups. Even though 1 out of the 3 groups got “fairly satisfactory” rating, the scores of the three groups have increased.

This is in line with the findings of Vandervelden & Siegel (1997) which suggested that effective word-recognition strategies permit children to quickly and automatically translate the letters or spelling patterns of written words into speech sounds so that they can identify words and gain rapid access to their meanings. As children learn to read more and more complex letter sound combinations, effective word-identification strategies will permit them to figure out the pronunciations of words they have never seen before in print. Students' semantic and syntactic knowledge, in turn, can help to confirm the accuracy of their attempts at word identification.

Table 5. Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Performance of the Kinder Pupils in Letter Sound Fluency

Group	Pretest	Posttest	Difference	t-test	p-value	Decision	Remark
Group 1 (Perfect Match)	83.07	85.00	1.93	2.132	0.026	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Group 2 (Fluency Letter Wheel)	85.93	94.64	8.71	4.240	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Group 3 (Letter Flash)	87.07	87.86	0.79	0.936	0.183	Do Not Reject H_{01}	Not Significant

Level of significance = 0.05

It is reflected in the data in Table 5 that there is a difference in the pretest and posttest scores of the pupils in terms of their performance in letter sound fluency. However, only in the utilization of Perfect Match (Group 1) and Fluency Letter Wheel (Group 2) that the p-values (0.026 and 0.000, respectively) are less than the level of significance (0.05). This means that there exists a significant difference of 1.93 in Group 1's and 8.71 in Group 2's pretest and posttest performance. This evidence suggests that the literacy intervention strategies, i.e., Perfect Match and Fluency Letter Wheel help the kinder pupils in attaining higher scores which would allow the rejection of the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test performance of the kinder pupils. This also implies that the utilization of the Perfect Match and Fluency Letter Wheel was a contributory factor and had an impact to the pupils that made them obtained very satisfactory and outstanding performance, respectively, in the posttest against their pretest. However, Letter Flash activity administered to Group 3 got a difference of 0.79 from the pre-test and post-test performance and a p-value of 0.183 which is greater than the level of significance (0.05). Although there is difference but only slight improvement, and this will not warrant the rejection of null hypothesis which states there is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test performance of the kinder pupils as far as the p-values of Group 3 is concerned. It also means that Letter Flash is not a contributory factor.

To sum up, the most notable among the three strategies is the Fluency Letter Wheel administered to Group 2 wherein a difference of 8.71 between the pretest (85.93) and the posttest (94.64) transmuted scores was attained. This alone can testify to the significance of the proposed intervention in increasing the word recognition ability of pupils.

This is in consonance with the findings of Klein (2012) which states that a systematic phonics instruction approach will bring about the greatest improvements in reading ability, especially for those students struggling with letter identification and letter sound recognition at the beginning of the kindergarten. As students master their alphabet knowledge, they can begin to build their phonemic awareness – the understanding of the ways that sounds function in words. Through early reading instruction, readers are taught to segment sounds, blend sounds, and identify words that begin or end with similar sounds. Students are then asked to create new words by substituting, adding, and/or deleting sounds in words. The goal of phonemic awareness is to teach children to associate sounds with individual letters.

Table 6. Word Recognition

Group	Pretest	Posttest	Difference	t-test	p-value	Decision	Remark
Group 1 (Familiar Word Readings)	78.71	78.86	0.15	0.124	0.452	Do Not Reject H_{01}	Not Significant
Group 2 (Word Relay)	79.93	81.93	2.00	2.876	0.006	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Group 3 (Fast Match)	80.57	92.86	12.29	8.471	0.000	Reject H_{01}	Significant

Level of Significance = 0.05

In Table 6, the data indicate that there is an increase in the posttest performances of the pupils in terms of word recognition. However only in the utilization of Word Relay (Group 2) and Fast Match (Group 3) that the p-values (0.006 and 0.000, respectively) are less than the level of significance (0.05). This finding allows rejection of the null hypothesis (H_{01}). This means that a significant difference exists between the pretest and posttest scores of the pupils. This also implies that the utilization of Word Relay and Fast Match in word recognition enables the pupils to attain satisfactory and outstanding performance in the posttest. On the other hand, the utilization of Familiar Word Readings got a difference of 0.15 and the p-value (0.452) is greater than the level of significance.

To sum up, a difference of 12.29 between the pretest (80.57) and post-test (92.86) scores of Group 3 using the intervention strategy Fast Match was attained. This difference indicates that the utilization of the said strategy enabled pupils to perform better. Although the respective differences of the remaining two groups were not that high, still an increase in their performance was noted as per Table 6. Thus, the strategies implemented have helped them attain higher scores.

This is in line with the findings of Rachmani (2011) which showed that evidence-based intervention that is designed appropriately with regard to focus, length of session and group size, can be effective in raising the emergent literacy knowledge of a group of four-year-old kindergarten children with low levels of emergent literacy knowledge. Phonological awareness addresses the sounds of the language. It is not about teaching the symbols, but rather it is teaching the sounds alone. It is one of the most important early indicators of reading success. Phonological awareness, especially phoneme awareness, is critically associated with literacy. Previous study of phonological awareness and reading in children in and out of school found that phonological awareness was associated with reading ability.

Table 7. Difference among the Post-Test Performance of the Kinder Pupils in Letter Sound Fluency

Source of Variation	SS	df	MSS	Computed F	p-value	Decision	Remark
Between-column	686.90	2	343.45	2.38	0.106	Do Not Reject H_{02}	Not Significant
With-in column	5,618.93	39	144.08				
Total	6,305.83	41					

Level of significance = 0.05

The data in Table 7 indicate that the computed value of p (0.106) is greater than the level of significance (0.05). This finding will not warrant rejection of the null hypothesis (H_{02}). This means that there is no significant difference among the posttest scores of the pupils. This also indicates that among the three proposed intervention strategies administered to the three different groups, there is not much evidence to prove that one strategy is better than the other. Although Fluency Letter Wheel strategy administered to Group 2 got the highest posttest score among the three, it has been found out that all three strategies contributed to the pupils' improvement of their scores.

Table 8. Difference among the Post-Test Performance of the Kinder Pupils in Word Recognition

Source of Variation	SS	df	MSS	Computed F	p-value	Decision	Remark
Between-column	1516.05	2	758.02	9.57	0.000	Reject H_{02}	Significant
With-in column	3090.36	39	79.24				
Total	4606.40	41					

Level of significance = 0.05

The data in Table 8 indicate that the computed value of p (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.06). This finding will allow rejection of the null hypothesis (H_{02}). This means that there is a significant difference among the posttest scores of the pupils. The post hoc analysis is presented on the next Table in order to identify which group or groups scored better in the posttest.

Table 9. Post Hoc Analysis of the Difference among the Post-Test Performance of the Kinder Pupils in Word Recognition

Variables	t	p-value	Decision	Remark
Familiar Word Readings ($\bar{x} = 78.86$) vs Word Relay ($\bar{x} = 81.93$)	0.91	0.367	Do not reject H_{02}	Not Significant
Familiar Word Readings ($\bar{x} = 78.86$) vs Fast Match ($\bar{x} = 92.86$)	4.16	0.000	Reject H_{02}	Significant
Word Relay ($\bar{x} = 81.93$) vs Fast Match ($\bar{x} = 92.86$)	3.25	0.002	Reject H_{02}	Significant

Level of Significance = 0.05

In the post hoc analysis presented in Table 9, the data indicate that between the utilization of Familiar Word Readings ($\bar{x} = 78.86$) and Fast Match ($\bar{x} = 92.86$), the latter strategy is better than the former ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$).

In addition between the utilization of Word Relay ($\bar{x} = 81.93$) and Fast Match ($\bar{x} = 92.86$), the latter strategy again is better than the former ($p = 0.002 < 0.05$).

This result is in consonance with the interview conducted by the researcher to the teacher who assisted in the administration of these intervention activities wherein the teacher

stressed that pupils are enjoying and having fun while doing the Fast Match activity as compared to Familiar Word Readings and Word Relay. Since they are so engaged with the activity, the learning becomes worthwhile and the inputs of the interventions strategies become more relatable and easy for them. The teacher added that Fast Match is the easiest and most convenient. The objective of the activity which is to gain speed and accuracy in reading words calls to affirm the results collected after the administration of the said activity. The pupils would really identify and match words to the same words placed on the other row. In addition, it is very convenient on the part of the teacher since they only need to prepare word cards, record sheet and pencil.

With regards to the use of familiar word readings ($\bar{x} = 78.86$) and word relay ($\bar{x} = 81.93$), the p-value is greater than the level of significance (0.05). This finding will not allow rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that there is no significant difference between the posttest scores of these groups and the utilization of Familiar Word Readings is not a contributory factor.

This is in line with the study of Hilbert and Eis (2014) exploring the characteristics and findings of an early literacy intervention program which was implemented to assist the development of the critical emergent literacy skills among kindergarten students identified at low-income and at-risk for delay in literacy skill development. The intervention reveals the effectiveness of early literacy intervention in the areas of vocabulary, phonological awareness, and print knowledge. The study suggests the possibility of preventing literacy delays and referrals for specialized, special education services for young children through early intervention at the preschool level.

Conclusions

In the light of the findings, the following conclusions are hereby drawn:

1. The pre-test performance of the kinder pupils in letter sound fluency is generally within satisfactory level. The pre-test performance of the kinder pupils in word recognition is also generally satisfactory. However, majority of the kinder pupils got a rating of less than 80%.
2. The post-test performance of the kinder pupils in letter sound fluency after the intervention is outstanding, with majority of the pupils got a very satisfactory rating.
3. The post-test performance of the kinder pupils in word recognition after the intervention is also remarkable, with Group 3 reaching the highest grade of 92. 86 among the three groups.
4. The utilization of the letter sound fluency intervention activities administered to Groups 1 and 2 indicated that these strategies helped these two groups attain higher scores. However, the strategy applied to Group 3 made only slight improvement in their post-test scores against their pre-test performance. Word recognition intervention activities administered to Groups 2 and 3 were also helpful in making them attain scores higher than the pretest. However, the strategy applied to Group 1 made only slight improvement in their post-test scores against their pre-test performance.
5. The result of the post-test after the literacy intervention strategies in letter sound fluency had been administered implied that not one proposed strategy is better than the others. All three strategies, therefore, contributed to the improvement of the pupils' performance. However, there is a significant difference among the posttest scores of the pupils in terms of word recognition. Therefore, a post hoc analysis is presented in order to identify which group or groups scored better in the posttest. In the post hoc analysis, it was found out that among the three proposed intervention strategies, Fast Match is the strategy which provided more help to the pupils in increasing fluency in word recognition.

Recommendations

In the light of findings and conclusions drawn, this is hereby recommended;

1. It is recommended that a study comparing the results of pupils who use the same literacy intervention strategies for letter sound fluency and word recognition be done in other schools and districts to affirm the findings of the study that the use of these literacy intervention strategies will significantly increase kinder pupils' letter sound fluency and word recognition.
2. It is also recommended that a thorough study and analysis be done regarding the connection of letter sound fluency and word recognition to a reader's reading comprehension.

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Appendix

(Survey Instrument)

EARLY GRADE READING ASSESSMENT PUPIL CONTEXT INTERVIEW SINUGBUANONG BINISAYA

Ask each question verbally to the child, as in an interview. Do not read the response option aloud. Wait for the child to respond, and then write this response in the space provided, or circle the code of the option that corresponds to the child's response. If there is no special instruction to the contrary, only one response is permitted.

1	Pila imong edad?	_____ years old Do not know/response.....9
2	Kanus-a ang imong birthday?	Month of _____ Do not know/response.....9
3	Unsang tuiga ka natawo?	Year _____ Do not know/response.....9
4a	Unsay inyong gigamit nga sinultian sa balay? <i>(Mahimo ang daghang tubag)</i>	Language spoken at home: _____
4b	Pareha ba ang sinultian nga gigamit ninyo sa balay ug sa eskuylahan? <i>(Mahimo ang daghang tubag)</i>	Do not know/response.....9 No.....0 Yes.....1
5	Naggamit ba mo og libro pagpraktis og basa sa ekuylahan?	Do not know/response.....9 No.....0 Yes.....1
6	Aduna ba kamoy lain nga mga basahon sa balay? <i>(Og naa, unsa man kini nga mga basahon?)</i>	Do not know/No response...9 <i>Not necessary to record the response.</i> No.....0 Yes.....1
7	<i>(Kon aduna sa No. 6)</i> Unsa man ang sinultian niining mga basahon? <i>(Mahimo ang daghang tubag)</i>	English.....1 Filipino.....2 Others (specify).....3 Do not know/response.....9
8	Aduna bay lain nga nagbasa sa balay?	No.....0 Yes.....1 Do not know/response.....9
9	<i>(Kon "Oo: ang tubag sa No. 8)</i> Kinsa man? <i>(Mahimo ang daghang tubag)</i>	Mother.....1 Father.....2 Sister/brother.....3 Others (specify).....4 Do not know/response.....9

EGRA Pupil Context Interview-Sinugbuanong Binisaya

Sa inyong balay, aduna ba kamoy:		Oo	Wala	Walay tubag
10	Radio?	1	0	9
11	Telepono	1	0	9
12	Kuryente?	1	0	9
13	Television?	1	0	9
14	Refrigerator?	1	0	9
15	Kasilyas sulod sa balay?	1	0	9
16	Bisikleta o trisikad?	1	0	9
17	Motorsiklo o tricycle?	1	0	9
18	Awto, van, o multicab?	1	0	9
19	Naka kindergarten ba ka una nag Grade 1?	No.....0 Yes.....1 Do not know/response.....9		
20	Unsang gradoha na ka karon?	Grade 1.....1 Grade 2.....2 Grade 3.....3 Grade 4.....4		
21	Unsang gradoha ka sa niaging tuig?	Not in school.....0 Grade 1.....1 Grade 2.....2 Grade 3.....3 Kindergarten.....8 Do not know/response.....9		
22	Maghatag ba og gimnuhaton ang imong magtutudlo?	No.....0 Yes.....1 Do not know/response.....9		
23	(Kon "Oo" ang tubag sa No. 22) Aduna bay motabang nimo sa imong mga gimbuhaton?	No.....0 Yes.....1 Do not know/response.....9		

Time completion:	at	_____:	_____
		am/pm	

EGRA Pupil Context Interview-Sinugbuanong Binisaya

EARLY GRADE READING ASSESSMENT TOOLKIT SINUGBUANONG BINISAYA

Student Name: _____
Grade and Section: _____
Name of Teacher: _____
Name of School: _____

Time started _____:_____ am/pm

COMPONENT 1. Orientation to Print

Show the child a decidable text.

Read the instructions in the boxes below; recording the child's response before moving the next instruction.

**Libro kini nga may mga istorya ug hulagway. Ayaw una basaha.
Niini nga panid, itudlo kanako kon asa ka magsugod og basa.**

[Child puts finger on the top row; left-most word]

Correct

Incorrect

No response

Karon, itudlo kanako unsay mosunod nga mga lulong ang imong basahon.

[Child moves finger from left to right]

Correct

Incorrect

No response

Pag-abot nimo sa tumoy sa linya, asa ka sunod mobasa?

[Child moves finger from left to right]

Correct

Incorrect

No response

EGRA Toolkit-Sinugbuanong Binisaya

COMPONENT 3a. Letter Sound Knowledge

Show the child the sheet of letters in the student stimuli booklet. Say:

Aniay panid sa mga letra sa alpabeto. Palihog isulti ang TINGOG sa mga letra kutob sa imong nahibaloan – akong usbon: ang TINGOG sa mga letra, dili ang NGALAN.

Pananglitan, [point to M] /m/ ang tingog niini nga letra, sama sa “MAMA.”

Magpraktis kita: Palihog isulti ang tingog niini nga letra [point to A]:

*If the child responds correctly, say: **Husto, /a/ ang tingog ani nga letra.***

*If the child responds correctly, say: **/a/ ang tingog ani nga letra.***

Magsulay kita og lain: Unsay tingog niini nga letra? [point to T]

*If the child does responds correctly say: **Husto, /t/ ang tingog niini nga letra.***

*If the child does not respond correctly, say: **/t/ ang tingog niini nga letra.***

Nasabtan ba?

Kon moingon ko nga “Sugod na,” palihog isulti dayon ang tingog sa mga letra. Isutli ang tingog sa mga letra gikan dinhi ug ipadayon hangtod sa katapusang linya. [Point to the first letter on the row after the example and draw your finger across the first line.] Kon adunay tingog nga dili ka kahibalo, tudloan ko ikaw. Apan kon kahibalo ka, maghilom ra ko ug maminaw. Andam ka na? Sugod na.

*Start the timer when the child reads the first letter: Follow along with your pencil and clearly mark any incorrect letters with a slash (/). Count self-corrections as correct. If you’ve already marked self-corrected letters as incorrect, circle the letter and go on. **Stay quiet**, except when providing answers as follows; if the child hesitates for 3 seconds, provide the name of the letter; point to the next letter and say **“Palihog padayon.”** Mark the letter you provide to the child as incorrect. If the student gives you the letter name, rather than the sound, provide the letter sound and say: **[Palihog isulti nako ang TINGOG sa letra”]**. This prompt may be given only once during the exercise.*

AFTER 60 SECONDS SAY, “hunong.” Mark the final letter read with a bracket (|)
Early stop rule: *If the child does not give a single correct response on the first line, say **“Salamat!”** and discontinue this exercise, check the box at the bottom, and go on to the next exercise.*

EGRA Toolkit-Sinugbuanong Binisaya

Pananglitan: m A T

M K t S y A n L P b [10]

g s L k A t d a N y [20]

S A p m y M L T k D [30]

G m B a T h w t s b [40]

S R d N p A r D E H [50]

U S H a M h g T n P [60]

w e s O W H u a t R [70]

r i h B s I G m ng U [80]

NG u N O e E r P k t [90]

L a D d i o ng E n Y [100]

Time remaining on stopwatch at completion (number of SECONDS)

Check the box if the exercise was discontinued because the child had no correct answer in the first line.

EGRA Toolkit-Sinugbuanong Binisaya

COMPONENT 4: Familiar Word Reading

Show the child the sheet of familiar words in the student stimuli booklet. Say:

Ania ang ubang mga pulong. Palihog basaha ang mga pulong nga imong nahibaloan. Ayaw i-spell ang mga pulong, hinoon, basaha kini. Pananglitan, kini nga pulong: “mata.”

Magpraktis kita: Palihog basaha kini nga pulong [point to the word “saya”]:

If the child responds correctly say: **Husto, “saya.”**

If the child does not respond correctly, say: **“saya” kini nga pulong.**

Magsulay kita og lain: Palihog basaha kini nga pulong [point to the word “tasa”]:

If the child responds correctly say: **Husto, “tasa.”**

If the child does not respond correctly, say: **“tasa” kini nga pulong.**

Kon moingon ko nga “Sugod na”, basaha dayon ang mga pulong sa tibuok panid. Pagsugod ubos sa linya. Maghilom ra ko ug maminaw, gawas kon mangayo ka og tabang. Nasabtan ba? Andam na ba ka? Sugod na.

*Start the timer when the child reads the first word: Follow along with your pencil and clearly mark any incorrect words with a slash (/). Count self-corrections as correct. If you’ve already marked self-corrected letters as incorrect, circle the letter and go on. **Stay quiet**, except when providing answers as follows; if the child hesitates for 3 seconds, provide the word; point to the next word and say **“Palihog padayon.”** Mark the word you provide to the child as incorrect.*

AFTER 60 SECONDS SAY, “hunong.” Mark the final word read with a bracket (|)

Early stop rule: *If the child does not give a single correct response on the first line, say **“Salamat!”** and discontinue this exercise, check the box at the bottom, and go on to the next exercise.*

EGRA Toolkit-Sinugbuanong Binisaya

Pananglitan:	mata	saya	tasa		
ka	mo	sa	og	ni	[10]
ug	kay	man	imo	ako	[20]
si	sad	dali	layo	nga	[30]
wala	apan	ikaw	gani	hain	[40]
ubos	unsa	kusog	hilom	tubag	[50]
labaw	kinsa	dayon	lugar	karon	[60]
baya	ugma	ingna	palit	inyong	[70]
daghan	gamay	buntag	dyotay	dugay	[80]
dungagi	gahapon	gagmay	kaligo	niingon	[90]
salamat	basahon	palihog	tubaga	kanus-a	[100]

Time remaining on stopwatch at completion (number of SECONDS)

Check the box if the exercise was discontinued because the child had no correct answer in the first line.

EGRA Toolkit-Sinugbuanong Binisaya

Activity Number 1

Perfect Match

Objective:

The kinder pupils will gain knowledge, speed and accuracy in recognizing letter sounds.

Materials:

- Initial sound picture cards (*choose 8 to 12 target sound picture cards*)
- Letter cards (*choose corresponding target letter sound cards*)
- Timer

Activity:

1. Separate initial sound picture cards and letter cards. Place cards face down in different rows. Place the timer at the center.
2. Teacher will set the timer to commence the matching. Taking turns, pupils will select a picture card and a letter card. Name the picture and say its initial sound (e.g., “ligid, /l/”). Name the letter and say its sound (e.g., “l, /l/”). Determine if the initial sound of the picture matches the selected letter.
3. If there is a match (e.g., ligid, “l” letter card), pick up cards,, place to the side, and take another turn. If cards do not match (e.g., iring, “b” letter card), return cards to their original positions and allow the next pupil to take a turn.
4. Continue until all match are found.
5. Time how long it takes to make all matches.

Activity Number 2

Fluency Letter Wheel

Objective:

The kinder pupils will gain speed and accuracy in recognizing letter-sounds.

Materials:

- Letter wheel spinner (*copy on card stock and cut*)
- Brad (*attach arrow to the spinner with the brad*)
- Letter-sound graph pupil sheet
- Cup
- Counters
- Timer
- Pencils

Activity:

1. Place the letter wheel spinner, cup, counters, and timer at the center. Provide the pupils with one letter-sound graph.
2. Teacher will set the timer to one minute and say begin.
3. The pupil will spin the arrow, names the letter, and say its sound (e.g., “t, /t/”)
4. If correct, the pupil will place one counter in the cup. If incorrect, no counter is placed in the cup.
5. Continue until the timer goes off.
6. Repeat activity attempting to increase speed and accuracy of letter-sound.
7. Continue until the pupil sheet is completed
8. Teacher will evaluate after.

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7				
6				
5				
4				
3				
2				
1				
	1	2	3	4

ROUNDS

Activity Number 3

Letter Flash

Objective:

The kinder pupils will gain speed and accuracy in recognizing letter-sounds.

Materials:

- Letter cards (choose a complete set of uppercase and lowercase letters)
- YES and NO header cards
- YES and NO graph pupil sheet (choose a graph based on the fluency level of pupil)
- Timer
- Pencils

Activity:

1. Place the letter cards face down in a stack. Place the YES and NO header cards face up next to each other. Place the timer at the center.
2. Teacher will set the timer to one (1) minute and tells the pupil to begin.
3. Pupil will select the top card, name the letter, and say its sound (e.g., “p, /p/”).
4. If correct, place the card in a pile under the YES header card. If incorrect, place it in a pile under the NO header card.
5. Continue until the timer goes off. Graph the number of cards in each pile in the corresponding columns on the student sheet.
6. Together, name the letters and say the sounds of the cards in the “NO” pile.
7. Repeat the activity attempting to increase accuracy.
8. Continue until the sheet is complete.
9. Teacher will evaluate after.

Activity Number 4

Familiar word readings

Objective:

The kinder pupils will gain speed and accuracy in recognizing familiar words.

Materials:

- Word practice sheet
- Correct-words-per-minute graph pupil sheet
- Timer
- Markers
- Pencils

Activity:

1. Place two copies of the target word practice sheet, timer, and marker at the center. Provide the pupil with a correct-words-per-minute graph.
2. Pupils practice reading the words aloud to classmates before beginning the time.
3. Teacher will set the timer for one (1) minute and tell the pupil to start.
4. Pupil will read the sheet while the teacher will follow on his copy and use a marker to mark any words that are read incorrectly. If all the words on the sheet are read, the pupil will go back to the top and continue reading.
5. When the timer goes off, the teacher will circle the last word read by the pupil and count the number of words read correctly.
6. Repeat the activity until attempting to increase the accuracy in recognizing words.
7. Teacher will evaluate later.

CORRECT WORDS PER MINUTE

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4			
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2			
1			

1ST try

2nd try

3rd try

SUGOD	KALAMAY	IRO
MAMA	HULMIGAS	ILAGA
PAPA	DAMA	SAPATOS
HAGDAN	DAMANG	MEDYAS
MAIS	SANINA	ULAN
TUBIG	PATIS	DAGAT
LATA	SUKA	ISDA
BASO	KUTSARA	SUD-AN
LALAKI	TINIDOR	KAN-ON
PULTAHAN	PLATO	HUMAY
BANGKO	DAHON	BUGAS
MUNYIKA	KAHOY	TUBO
NUKOS	TANOM	BUSAY
HARI	BABOY	SAPA
MATA	KANDING	SUBA
ILONG	KABAW	SABAW
TIYAN	IRING	INIT

Activity Number 5

Word Relay

Objective:

The kinder pupils will gain speed and accuracy in reading words.

Materials:

- Word cards
- Correct-words-per-minute record sheet
- Timer
- Pencils

Activity:

1. Place the word cards face down in a stack. Place the timer in the center. Place also the record sheet.
2. The teacher sets the timer for one minute. Taking turns, pupil one selects the top card from the stack and reads the word.
3. If correct, the pupil places the card aside. If incorrect, pupil makes attempts while teacher counts to three. If still unable to read it, place it at the bottom of the stack.
4. Continue until the timer goes off. Count and record the number of words read correctly on the record sheet.
5. Repeat the activity attempting to increase speed and accuracy.
6. Continue until the record sheet is complete.

CORRECT WORDS PER MINUTE

1 st Try	_____ words per minute
2 nd Try	_____ words per minute
3 rd Try	_____ words per minute
4 th Try	_____ words per minute
5 th Try	_____ words per minute

Activity Number 6

Fast Match

Objective:

The kinder pupils will gain speed and accuracy in reading words.

Materials:

- Word cards
- Record sheet
- Timer
- Pencils

Activity:

1. Provide pupils with a set of word cards. Place the timer at the center. Prepare also a record sheet to record the time consumed to finish the activity.
2. Teacher places the word cards face up in two rows with the same words arranged differently.
3. When pupil picks a word from row 1, he will then look for the same word in row 2.
4. If a match is made, pupil picks up both words, reads them (i.e., “tubig, tubig”) and places the matching cards in a stack. If a match is not made, another pupil will do the activity.
5. Continue until all words are matched. Stop the timer for each pupil and record the time on the student sheet.
6. Repeat activity attempting to increase speed and accuracy.